

A Study to Adopt the Primary Schools' Children on Number Conservation Ability through Piaget's Cognitive Theory

Muhammad Naseer Ud Din

Associate Professor, Institute of Education & Research, Kohat University of Science & Technology, Kohat, KP, Pakistan.
Email: naseerkust@yahoo.com

Muhammad Zaigham Qadeer

Associate Professor, Faculty of Education, AIOU, Islamabad, Pakistan.

Mumtaz Gul Khan

Assistant Professor, Department of Educational Development, Chilas Campus, Karakoram International University, Gilgit Baltistan, Pakistan.

Abstract

The main objectives of this study were: (1) To determine the accomplishment of conservation ability among the primary school children (2) To compare the conservation ability of the rural and urban school children and male and female school children. The population was all the primary schools in Kohat District. Four urban as well as two rural schools were taken as a sample of the study. In the above-mentioned sample, 160 students were randomly selected 80 from rural and 80 from urban. And from rural 40 male and 40 females as well as from urban 40 male and 40 females were selected for the study. Researchers have personally visited and administered the conservative capacity (CAT) tasks of students. For data analysis percentage was used. The children of rural school perform better than urban school students because late school enrolment and the performance of females are slightly better than that of male school children.

Key Words:

Conservation Ability, Piaget's Cognitive Development, Conservative ability Task

Introduction

Education is the Key factor which changes the conduct of a student happens in its general sense, instruction is a mode of learning in which knowledge, mental health, or actions of a group of people are shared from one year to the next through teaching, planning, or exploring. Piaget 's scholarly development theory has real educational consequences. The revelations from Piaget have had an effect on educational programs, instruction and tutoring evaluation, especially for arithmetic purposes. The point of this investigation was to decide Piaget's idea of psychological improvement especially his idea of achievement of protection and to watch that either neighborhood offspring of Kohatian perform similarly on Piagetian subjective assignments to others in somewhere else and that environmental factors, for example, urbanization and sexual orientation factors are also identified with intellectual advancement or not.

Education is the fundamental power to get the hang of anything, yet it ought to accord to the psychological level of the kid. Training is the principal factor that leads to change the conduct of students. To educate adequately, the educators must recognize various hypotheses of learning. Every individual has the capacity of learning. Learning is a, "moderately lasting change in a living being's conduct because of experience" (Arif, 1992)

Learning is a procedure that unites subjective, passionate, and natural impacts and encounters for gaining, upgrading, or rolling out improvements in a single's information, attitudes, qualities, and world perspectives (Arif, 2003; Aschraft, 1994).

Concept of Learning

Learning begins the day that a human has been created and that happens in all everyday issues. School learning is just a small part of the learning process. The greater part of analysts and teachers depict learning as a procedure that causes to change or adjust the conduct of the individuals through making them involved or preparing. As indicated by Hamachek (1995), it alludes not exclusively to a result that is clearly recognizable, yet in addition to states of mind, sentiments and scholarly procedures that may not be self-evident. Gagné (1964) stated that "learning is an adaptation of human behavior or capacity that can be maintained and is not merely ascribable to the process of development."

As per Reid (2008), learning is a procedure that causes any adjustment in conduct not only to be logically improved. This tends to be more limited to the psychological, but the psychomotor could be

added (e.g. taking part in a game or a melodic instrument, or different abilities such as swimming, driving, etc.). The issues of knowledge-based exercise in learning and data capacity are under discussion in the field of informative research.

Learning hypothesis, as explained by Pavlov, Watson and Skinner enormously affected reasoning skills about adolescence amid the main portion of the twentieth century. Pavlov established the framework of the art of learning. John Watson established a framework of the school of behaviorism in brain science. Skinner investigated the idea of operant conduct, where the life form is controlled by the outcomes of its activities. In the contending hypothetical perspectives in brain science, Piaget gives a far-reaching hypothesis of discernment. Piaget's hypothesis of perception puts the required weight on considering importance of youth (Arif, 2003).

Piaget's Theory of Cognitive Development

Jean Piaget's school interests at first were in science, in the meantime, he wound up enthused about adolescents' academic change; he put over the latest sixty extensive stretches of his life gathering an astonishing measure of research information identifying with mental headway (Wadsworth, 1984). Notwithstanding his profound established work with adolescents and his extensively perceived responsibilities to explore the mind, Piaget's acquaintance is philosophical as contradicted with mental. Hyde (1970) has delineated made by Piaget as that of trying, by the prompt system for question and answer, to discover in what ways a youth's reasoning fluctuates from that of an adult.

Piaget delineated scholarly progression as a system of acclimation to nature and an increase of natural change (Wadsworth, 1984). Piaget depicted discernment as a dynamic and natural process (Witkin, 1978). Piaget's concept of scholarly headway was colossally affected by his underlying work as a researcher where he wound up roused by the relationship of mollusks with their condition. From this recognition, he came to assume that "characteristic showings are exhibitions of acclimation to the physical condition and relationship of condition" (Wadsworth, 1984). He found that the mind and the body don't work unreservedly of each other, driving him to see the possibility of insightful progression in a much same course as a common change. He assumed that academic and common activities are the two areas of a general method by which a living thing acclimates to the earth and masterminds understanding (Wadsworth, 1984).

Piaget saw a child as a living being that creates in a circumstance; that impacts its headway and acclimation to the earth. He asserted that a child endeavors to comprehend the articles around him and manufactures data through experiences gave by the earth. Through his examinations, he found that youths pick up remarkably as opposed to adults. As a researcher, he watched and inspected the methodology of an adolescent's thinking and learning. He endeavored to explore the effect of a tyke's area and experiences on his mental headway (Atkinson, 1983).

Piaget's concept of subjective change stages is a basic bit of his speculation. Observation suggests the mental methodology connected with getting data and comprehension, including considering, knowing, reviewing, judging, and basic reasoning (Atkinson, 1983).

Piaget's perception gathers a very few positions on the possibility of change. (a) Stage progression is invariant; (b) Growth is disconnected into subjectively exceptional periods; (c) Stages imply certain general traits; (d) All stages address hierarchic compromises; and (e) Stages spread out in a comparative plan paying little respect to the social assortments. The progress of perception is fundamentally broken down into three stages: sensory motor, concrete operation and formal operation. Nevertheless, there are various periods, which depict availability, achievement, and advancement of these stages. Concrete operational stage particularly encounters a more drawn out time of preparation, which is generally, called pre-operational period. (Wadsworth, 1984)

Conservation

Conservation is the most celebrated of every single consistent task related to the phase of solid activities level of Piaget's hypothesis of scholarly improvement. Preservation signifies, "Understanding that amount, length or number of things is irrelevant to the game plan or appearance of the protector items"(Piaget, 1972).

As indicated by Piaget (1972) Conservation alludes to a capacity inconsistent reasoning as indicated by the analyst Jean Piaget amid third stage, the solid operational stage, the offspring of age 7-11 acs this capacity, to intelligently verify that a specific amount will continue as before in spite of change of the compartment, shape, or evident size. Conservation assignments test a youngster's capacity to see that a few properties are preserved or invariant after protest experiences of physical change. Protection itself is characterized by the capacity to remember what remains unchanged and what changes in a question after it has been changed stylishly. One who can ration can switch the change rationally and comprehend remuneration.

Piaget's most well-known undertaking (there are numerous others e.g. protection of substance, weight, number and so on) included demonstrating a tyke two measuring glasses, both of which were indistinguishable and which contained a similar measure of fluid. The tyke was asked whether the two measuring agencies had a similar measure of fluid in both. At that point fluid from one of the glasses was filled with a taller, more slender glass. The tyke was then asked whether there was as yet a similar measure of fluid in the two glasses. A kid who can't rationally reply "No, there is more in the tall thin glass".

He proposed that this disarray was conceived from a pre-operational tyke's powerlessness to comprehend the thought of reversibility; the capacity to see the inversion of a physical change and in addition the change itself. These thoughts were utilized to make the 'Rule of Invariance'.

The ages at which youngsters can finish protection errands have been addressed by consequent research. Research has recommended that asking a similar inquiry twice drives youthful kids to change their answer as they accept that they are being asked again in the light of the fact that they missed the point first time around. The significance of setting was likewise accentuated by specialists who modified the assignment so that a 'mischievous teddy' changed the cluster as opposed to an experimenter themselves. This appeared to give kids an explanation without mistakes behind the second inquiry being asked and decreased the age at which youngsters finished the tests. Grade school going age is an imperative stage in the passionate and mental advancement of a kid. School can possibly give invigorating mental encounters, which can be extremely helpful for the solid development of a youngster. This investigation was proposed to check the accomplishment of the capacity of Conservation among grade school kids in area Kohat.

Statement of the Problem

Primary school going age is a very important phase in the emotional and mental development of a child. This proposed study is designed to explore the ability of the accomplishment of primary school children to conserve.

Objective of the Study

Main Objectives of this Were

To find out how primary school children develop their conservation abilities.

1. To compare the conservation ability of rural and urban school children.
2. To compare male and female school children's conservation ability.

Hypothesis of the Study

To achieve the aims of this study, hypotheses were established.

1. Conservation capacity is accomplished among children in primary school.
2. Students in rural school with more traditional skills relative to students in urban schools had better performance.

Delimitation of the Study

The present study includes all type of primary schools, but as per Piaget's cognitive theory, "cognitive stages are universal" therefore study was delimited to four primary schools in district Kohat. These schools were selected from both rural and urban areas.

Methods and Procedure

Research demands an examination of issues logically to discover some serviceable arrangement. The point of this investigation was to decide Piaget's idea of psychological improvement especially his ideas of protection and to find what offspring of elementary school musings about preservation were and what confusions they may have. What's more, either Kohatian tyke performs similarly on Piagetian psychological errands to others in the nation and somewhere else. The Environmental factors, for example, urbanization and sexual orientation factors are also identified with intellectual advancement.

Population

All primary schools in Kohat District (KPK) were part of the study population.

Sample

Table 1 List of School

Category	Schools
Urban	2
Rural	2
Total	4

The study included four schools, two urban schools and two rural schools.

Table 2 Sample of students (List of students)

Category	Male	Female	Grade 4 th		Grade 5 th		Total
			M	F	M	F	
Urban	40	40	20	20	20	20	80
Rural	40	40	20	20	20	20	80
Total	80	80	40	40	40	40	160

In the above-mentioned sample, 160 students were randomly selected 80 from rural and 80 from urban. And from rural 40 male and 40 females as well as from urban 40 male and 40 female of Grade 4th and 5th twenty from each grade with an equal proportion of both the gender were selected for the study.

Research Instruments

Researchers have prepared seven tasks in Kohat District to test the achievement of conservative abilities among primary school children.

Conservation of Length

For longitudinal preservation, two eight-inch long plastic pieces are laid parallel and their edges are exactly the same. The tyke questioned whether the sticks were of the same length when the child was confident that they were of the same length. Then one walks a little and asks the under-studies what's going on longer. Tyke Conserver said the two sticks were the same length.

Conservation of Weight

Two plastic balls of the same size have been given to the study and needed to determine their weight, are likely to be identical in weight. Each of them has been pinched. Moreover, asked again which one is heavier? The child preserver responds that both are equally heavy bundles.

Conservation of Area

Take and arrange four blocks of the same size plastics in the focus of a paper and ask for the study that shows the territory these squares have occupied if masterminded towards the edges of a paper and ask the understudies whether they may or may not take a similar area. The conserving kid should reply that there is no effect on the area protected by pieces on the difference in the square situation.

Conservation of amount of Substance

Take two rubber bands and width of the same length and give the tyke, and ask them to take the same elasticity. They'd say yes, then one is rolled up and the investigation has been carried again, which is more elastic? The retaining type shows the same length for both elastic classes.

Conservation of Quantity of Items

Two different types of similar plastic blocks are arranged with different sizes, 6 x 2 and 4 x 3. In addition, the understudies asked which type includes additional pieces. Conserver younger people will respond that both forms express pieces firmly.

Conservation of Liquid Volume

Two identical A and B glasses are equivalent in length of the bath. The tyke asks, "Does water have a similar amount in those two glasses?" The boy responds they are the same. The water in Glass B is then combined with

a strong thin glass and the tyke sees glass A and C. Similar investigation is being reshuffled. The irrigation tyke for both glasses will again be replaced by the same water level

Conservation in Situations Supported by Logical Reason

Two figures are written on a ledger, one of which is $24 + 42=66$ and the understudies asked at that point what the suitable answer might be $42 + 24=?$ When you underestimate information in order to test them, this means that you do not track them and, when you judge their reversibility, it means that you keep them.

Data Collection

The researchers visited the sample schools personally and all these tasks were carried out by the students.

Data Analysis

Then the researchers arranged the data in a systematic way and organized the data in the form of a table. Data collected through tasks. Tasks were tabled and data analyzed using graphic and percentages methods.

Results and Discussion

The main aim of this study was to test that primary school children in Kohat district have conservative abilities, according to Piaget cognitive theory." For this purpose, seven different type tasks have been carried out in order to obtain the data of the respondents. The nature of the study was therefore descriptive. This section deals with the analysis and interpretation of the data generated by the percentage of tasks.

Responses to the Task Male Rural

Table 3. Conservative Ability Task (CAT) of Jurma Public School (Male Rural)

Responses	No. of Students	CAT	Total	%age						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
Satisfactory		14	16	14	17	18	15	18	112	80%
Unsatisfactory		6	4	6	3	2	5	2	28	20%
Total	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	140	100%

The results have shown in Table 3 describe the responses of the rural school male children of grade 4th and 5th to the conservation tasks in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 20 rural male students give 80 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 20 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Table 4 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) of Dhoda Public School (Male Rural)

Responses	No. of Students	CAT	Total	%age						
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
Satisfactory		12	12	10	10	10	10	10	74	53%
Unsatisfactory		8	8	10	10	10	10	10	66	47%
Total	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	140	100%

The results shown in Table 4 describe the responses of the rural school male children of grade 4th and 5th to the conservation tasks in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 20 Male rural students give 53 % satisfactory responses to the tasks while 47 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Table 5 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) both Rural Male Schools

Schools	No. of Students	Satisfactory Responses and %age	Unsatisfactory Responses and %age
CAT of Jurma Public School	20	112 (80%)	28 (20%)
CAT of Dhoda Public School	20	74 (53%)	66 (47%)
Total	40	186 (66%)	94 (34%)

The conservation tasks in terms of the response category gave the tasks to each student. 40 rural male students gave 66 % satisfactory responses to the tasks, whereas, 34% unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence, it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Responses to the Task Female Rural

Table 6 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) of Jurma Public School (Female Rural)

Responses	No. of Students	CAT 1	CAT 2	CAT 3	CAT 4	CAT 5	CAT 6	CAT 7	Total	%age
Satisfactory		19	17	17	17	17	19	18	124	88%
Unsatisfactory		1	3	3	3	3	1	2	16	12%
Total	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	140	100%

The results, shown in Table 6 describe the responses of the rural school female children of grade 4 and 5 to the conservation tasks in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 20 rural female students gave 88 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 12 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Table 7 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) of Dhoda Public School (Female Rural)

Responses	No. of Students	CAT 1	CAT 2	CAT 3	CAT 4	CAT 5	CAT 6	CAT 7	Total	%age
Satisfactory		16	11	16	13	16	17	16	105	75%
Unsatisfactory		4	9	4	7	4	3	4	35	25%
Total	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	140	100%

The results shown in Table 7, describe the responses of the rural school female children of grade 4 and 5 to the conservation tasks in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 20 rural female students give 75 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 25 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence, it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Table 8 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) Both Female Rural Schools

Schools	No. of Students	Satisfactory Responses and %age	Unsatisfactory Responses and %age
CAT of Jurma Public School	20	124 (88%)	16 (12%)
CAT of Dhoda Public School	20	105 (75%)	35 (25%)
Total	40	229 (82%)	51 (18%)

The results shown in Table 8, describe the responses of both rural school female children of grade 4 and 5 to the conservation tasks in terms of the response category they specified for each of the tasks. 40 rural female students gave 82 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 18 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Responses to the Task Male Urban

Table 9 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) of Working Folks Grammar School (Male Urban)

Responses	No. of Students	CAT 1	CAT 2	CAT 3	CAT 4	CAT 5	CAT 6	CAT 7	Total	%age
Satisfactory		15	13	9	8	6	10	10	71	51%
Unsatisfactory		5	7	11	12	14	10	10	69	49%
Total	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	140	100%

The results shown in Table 9 describe the responses of the urban school male children of grade 4th and 5th to the conservation task in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 20 Male Urban students give

51 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 49 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Table 10 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) of Cantonment public school Kohat (Male Rural)

Responses	No. of Students	CAT 1	CAT 2	CAT 3	CAT 4	CAT 5	CAT 6	CAT 7	Total	%age
Satisfactory		13	16	15	13	13	17	17	104	74%
Unsatisfactory		7	4	5	7	7	3	3	36	26%
Total	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	140	100%

The results shown in Table 10 describe the responses of the urban school male children of grade 4th and 5th to the conservation task in terms of the response category they specified for each of the tasks. 20 Male Urban students gave 74 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 26 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Table 11 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) Both Urban Male Schools

Schools	No. of Students	Satisfactory Responses and %age	Unsatisfactory Responses and %age
CAT of Working Folks Grammar School	20	71 (51%)	69 (49%)
CAT of Cantonment School	20	104 (74%)	36 (26%)
Total	40	175 (63%)	105 (37%)

The results shown in Table 11, describe the responses of both of urban male school children of grade 4 and 5 to the conservation task in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 40 Male Urban students gave 63 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 37 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Responses to the Task Female Urban

Table 12 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) of Working Folks Grammar school (Female Urban)

Responses	No. of Students	CAT 1	CAT 2	CAT 3	CAT 4	CAT 5	CAT 6	CAT 7	Total	%age
Satisfactory		17	15	15	14	12	17	18	108	77%
Unsatisfactory		3	5	5	6	8	3	2	32	23%
Total	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	140	100%

The results shown in Table 12, describe the responses of the urban school of female children of grade 4 and 5 to the conservation task in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 20 Female Urban students give 77 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 23 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Table 13. Conservative Ability Task (CAT) of Cantonment public school Kohat (Female Rural)

Responses	No. of Students	CAT 1	CAT 2	CAT 3	CAT 4	CAT 5	CAT 6	CAT 7	Total	%age
Satisfactory		17	15	12	13	16	13	16	102	73%
Unsatisfactory		3	5	8	7	4	7	4	38	27%
Total	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	140	100%

The results shown in Table 13 describe the responses of the urban school female children of grade 4 and 5 to the conservation task in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 20 Female Urban students give 73 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 27 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Table 14 Conservative Ability Task (CAT) Both Female Urban Schools

Schools	No. of Students	Satisfactory Responses and %age	Unsatisfactory Responses and %age
CAT of Working Folks Grammar School	20	108(77%)	32 (23%)

CAT of Cantonment School	20	102 (73%)	38 (27%)
Total	40	210 (75%)	70 (25%)

The results shown in Table 14, describe the responses of both urban school female children of grade 4 and 5 to the conservation task in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 40 Female Urban students give 75 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 25 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Hence it indicates that although these students are in the concrete operational stage, they were not fully matured.

Overall Data of Rural and Urban Schools

Table 15 Overall Data of Rural and Urban Schools

S. No	Category	Gender	Number of students	CAT	
				Satisfactory/Total CAT WITH %AGE	Unsatisfactory/Total CAT WITH %AGE
1	RURAL	MALE	40	186/280 66%	94/280 34%
2	RURAL	FEMALE	40	229/280 82%	51/280 18%
TOTAL	RURAL	MALE + FEMALE	80	415/560 74%	145/560 26%
3	URBAN	MALE	40	175/280 63%	105/280 37%
4	URBAN	FEMALE	40	210/280 75%	70/280 25%
TOTAL	URBAN	MALE + FEMALE	80	385/560 69%	175/560 31%

The results shown in Table 15, describe the responses of all the urban/rural school male/female children of grade 4 and 5 to the conservation task in terms of the response category they gave to each of the tasks. 80 male/female rural students gave 74 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 26 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks as compared to the 80 male/female urban students give 69 % satisfactory responses to the tasks and 31 % unsatisfactory responses to the tasks. Difference between Urban and Rural is 5 %, which means Rural Male / Female give 5% more satisfactory responses as compared to Urban Male /Female. Rural Female students give 14 % more responses as compared to Rural Male. Urban Female gives 12 % more responses as compared to Urban Male. Rural Female gives 7 % more responses as compared to Urban Female. Rural Male gives 3 % more responses as compared to urban male.

Discussion

The research was planned to investigate how primary school children are conserved. The outline of the examination was formative and cross-sectional. The research based on Piaget 's empirical theories, in which youthful children arrange their eyes and challenge longevity in the midst of the tangible motor. The preparatory organization requires the creation of the symbolic idea to illustrate the extended use of dialect. In the robust operational level, young people will carry out vital tasks, such as classification and serial application of solid objects. In the last step, systematic tasks and understudies improve the capacity to think and mentally interact. Protection alludes to a capacity inconsistent reasoning as per the clinician Jean Piaget amid the third stage, the solid operational organize, the offspring of age 7-11 experts this capacity, to sensibly verify that a specific amount will continue as before notwithstanding alteration of the holder, shape, or evident size. Protection undertakings test a kid's capacity to see that a few properties are monitored or invariant after a question experiences physical change idea of preservation and explored whether the youngsters had the capacity to comprehend this idea or not. As indicated by Piaget's and different researchers, for example, Flavell (1963), and Younnis and Dean (1986), children achieved this capacity at 6- or 7-years ago level.

Distinctive assortments of protection are not accomplished all the while. Preservation of strong and fluid obtained at around seven or eight years old, that of weight at nine or ten years and of volume at around eleven or twelve years. Much research has been conveyed to verify the ages at which youngsters accomplish different sorts of protection. These

Investigations have been directed for the most part in the western world. To check the achievement of Conservative capacity, seven undertakings were created including protection of number, preservation of fluid

volume, preservation of length, preservation of measure of substance, preservation of territory, preservation of number of things, protection of weight, preservation in circumstances upheld by a legitimate reason.

The right answers presumably mirror the level of youngsters' attention to the basic intricacy of each errand. This leads us to infer that through these undertakings a few understudies turned out to be progressively mindful of the auxiliary association of these errands, while different understudies dismiss the basic association of the development. Examination of the reactions to the undertaking on preservation demonstrated that there is a solid relationship between protection of these errands and comprehension of the basic multifaceted nature of the estimation assignments, prompting right count of these undertakings for all conservers as reason speculatively.

As indicated by this investigation, the preservation capacity was observed to be an element of developing age since this capacity tended to increment with developing age. However, full accomplishment of protection of uprooted volume is as yet not found in the class fifth where the period of kid is roughly 11-12 years. The aftereffect of the present examination consequently vary from Piaget's definition yet this outcome bolsters the discoveries of Younnis (1971), Brainerd (1979), Uzgirris (1964)). As indicated by the above analysts in kids over the age of 12 years achieved the volume protection capacity.

Notwithstanding decide the protection in the Primary school, the present examination subject to discover the distinctions between male and female and provincial/urban foundation, in preservation capacity. Contrasts were found among young men and young ladies and from the provincial/urban foundation. Be that as it may, this is because generally enrolment of kids in country regions. This discovering underpins Piaget's hypothesis which accentuation that such progression in scholarly advancement as protection capacities are for the most part consequences of inherited factors, for example, age and development, instead of ecological variables. He says that scholarly advancement is widespread which does not vary from culture to culture.

The study present examination requires to assist confirmation by taking the bigger example as well as by including accurate age factor of the understudies and other instructively vital factors that were not been mulled over in the present investigation.

By studying the phases of Piaget, the teacher can understand how the child subjectively develops while the teacher designs suitable tasks to create a balanced understudy. Whitehurst and Zimmerman, 1979 have also shown that explorations have been impractical in order to specifically instruct psychological change. Piaget trusted that the measure of time every kid spends in each stage shifts by condition (Kamii, 1982).

Conclusions

Based on findings and results the following conclusions were made for the change of Conservative capacity among primary school children.

1. Assessment of the answers to the conservation challenge shows that the children's mind functions cognitively. It shows that children in class 4 are relatively low-conservative ability compared to children in class 5
2. The majority of the students of class 5 are still at the middle to mature level of concrete operations.
3. In fact, in Kohat district, primary school children have the same potential for conservation as elsewhere. Because of late school attendance, rural school children with a significantly more conservative ability compared with urban school children. The performance of female children was slightly better than that of the male children
4. Such gender disparities between children and primary schools in urban or rural areas underpin Piaget's hypothesis that changes in intellectual and development skills are largely triggered by genetic factors such as age and maturation instead of environmental factors. He says that intellectual development is universal and does not differ from culture to culture. Gender appears to have had an impact on the development of child conservation and, in the same order demographics have also had an impact on the conservation capacity of primary school children.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions the following suggestions were made for the change of Conservative capacity among elementary school children.

1. It is found that teachers were not familiar with the conservative ability of children. Teachers must understand the levels at which their students are functioning and should try to ascertain their students' cognitive level to adjust their teaching accordingly. By emphasizing conservation, the teacher provides critical direction so that the child can discover concepts through investigation. The child should be

encouraged to self-check, approximate, reflect and reason while the teacher studies the Childs work to better understand his thinking.

2. During the examination, it is watched that Conservative capacity isn't given appropriate consideration in the showing points of essential level arithmetic and in different subjects in Pakistan, in spite of the fact that it is essential for understanding the related idea in the subject of science and mathematics. The educational modules organizers need to give reasonable place to this subject both as a point for thinking about and as an apparatus for the advancement of understudy's moderate capacity. Numerous science and day by day life exercises be utilized as a part of along these lines to give understudies issues of protection and ought to be permitted to take care of issues in an assortment of ways and settings.
3. As the present investigation depended on a little example and age factor which is most powerful isn't thought about appropriately. In this manner, the examination is imitated with the substantial populace and with considering age factor.
4. Conservative capacity to be explored among youngsters living in various situations, for example, uncommon schools, halfway houses, Madrassas and in workshops.
5. Comparison of the cognitive ability of Kohatian children with children of elsewhere requires a detailed and updated survey of latest research in this field.

References

- Arif, M.H. 2003. Human Development and Learning. Majeed Book Depot, Lahore, Pakistan. pp.163-180.
- Arif, M.H. 1992. Advance Educational Psychology. 1st ed. Majeed Book Depot, Lahore, Pakistan. pp.245-253.
- Ashcraft, M. H. (1994). Human memory and cognition. New York, Harper Collins College.
- Atkinson, C. (1983), Making Sense of Piaget, Boston Mass., USA.
- Brainerd, C. J. (1979). A neo Piagetian model of children's concept learning. Le Bulletin de Psychologie, in Press.
- Flavell, J. H. (1963). The Developmental Psychology of Jean Piaget. New York, Canada, London: Van Nostrand Reinhold Company Monographs of the Society for Research in Child Development, 29, (2, Serial No. 93).
- Gagné, R. M. (1964). Problem solving. In A.W. Melton (Ed.), Categories of Human Learning. New York: Academic Press.
- Hamechek, D. (1995), Psychology in teaching, learning and growth. USA: Allyn & Bacon
- Hyde, J. S., Fennema, E., Lamon, S. J. (1990). Gender differences in mathematics performance: A meta-analysis. Psychological Bulletin, 107, 139-155.
- Kamii, C. (1982). Number in preschool and kindergarten: Educational implications of Piaget's theory. Washington, DC: National Association for the Education of Young Children.
- Piaget, J. (1972). Intellectual evolution from adolescence to adulthood. Human Development, 15, 1-12.
- Reid, N. (2008) *Landmarks in Assessment*, Unpublished monograph, Centre for Science Education, University of Glasgow, Glasgow
- Uzgiris, I. C. (1964). Situational generality of conservation. Child Development, 35(3), 831-841.
- Wadsworth, J.B. (1984). Piaget's Theory of Cognitive and Affective Development. Longman Publishing Group. London.UK
- Witkin, H. A. (1978). Cognitive styles in personal and cultural adaptation. Worcester, MA: Clark University Press.
- Younnis, I., & Dean, A. (1971). Judgement and imaging aspects of operations: A Piagetian study with Korean and Costa Rican children. Child Development, 42, 1837-1847.
- Younnis, J. (1971). Classificatory schemes in relation to class inclusion before and after training. Human Development, 14, 1020-1031.
- Zimmerman, B. J., & Whitehurst, G. J. (1979). Structure and function: A comparison of two views of the development of language and cognition. In G. J. Whitehurst and B. J. Zimmerman (Eds.),